

North Devon Marine Natural Capital Plan

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North Devon Biosphere

www.northdevonbiosphere.org.uk/mncp

Photo: Neville Stanikk

North Devon Marine Pioneer

- Pioneers were set up to test ideas to deliver the 25 Year Environment Plan
- 4 Pioneers
 - Catchment in Cumbria (EA)
 - Urban in Greater Manchester (EA)
 - Landscape in North Devon (NE)
 - Marine over 2 sites: North Devon Biosphere and Suffolk Coasts and heaths AONB (MMO)

Photo: Neville Stanikk

Marine Pioneer – trialling 25 Year Environment Plan (25YEP) delivery

Gathering supporting information

Links between ecosystems and ecosystem services in Marine Pioneer (SWEEP/UoP)

The North Devon Marine Asset and Risk register (SWEEP/UoP)

The methodology to incorporate Natural Capital into a sustainability assessment (SWEEP/PML)

A geodatabase and online geonode (Plymouth University)

Identifying funding models for sustainable finance (WWF/BR)

PhD research: Beth Wills University of Surrey; Rachel Holtby; Northumbria University

Demonstrating the Approach

Testing the natural capital approach to saltmarsh restoration (SWEEP/Biosphere)

Bristol Channel Herring project (BLUE/D&S IFCA/Swansea University)

Fisheries Research and Management Plans (FRMP)(D&S IFCA/Biosphere)

MPA governance toolkit (WWF/NE)

MPA compass survey (WWF)

Comms and engagement: Journey to the Sea films; waste shark; Biosphere website

Collaboration and knowledge exchange

- Marine Working Group
- Fishers, Scientist and Managers Partnership
- Other fora and groups in the area
- Governance analysis (WWF/Sky Ocean Rescue)
- Research - Marine Pioneer PhDs, and others

Local 25 YEP delivery - Natural Capital Plans

These will be aligned with the
25 Year Environment Plan

**but be particularly relevant
to the local area or
geographies within them.**

Leaving the environment in a
better state than we found it.

A Green Future: Our 25 Year Plan to Improve the Environment

The development of the plan

First Marine Working Group March 2017 – long term goals for North Devon Biosphere's Marine Area.

North Devon Marine Asset and Risk Register – identifying priorities.

Marine Working Group workshops, FSMP, and other expert groups – bringing people along and identifying aims, opportunities and actions.

Governance assessments – what was needed and how could we do it in North Devon

Sustainable finance - identifying investment opportunities and where that investment might come from*

25 year vision for the marine area of the North Devon Biosphere:

Thriving wildlife and **clean water**, and **protected habitats** to support them.

The people of North Devon will have **input into the governance of the marine area** and will feel involved and useful in decision-making.

Nature will support a **prosperous fishing industry** and **other maritime industries**.

Nature will be considered as a **whole system**, recognising that land and sea are intrinsically linked, and local decisions will reflect this.

Clean growth in the **tourism sector** and **land-based activities** will consider **impacts on the sea** and mitigate those issues.

The people of North Devon will feel the benefits of a healthy and recovering natural environment through **increased wellbeing**.

Aims defined within the 25 year vision:

AM01. ACHIEVE SUSTAINABLE AND VIABLE WILD-CAPTURE FISHERIES

AM02. CREATE NEW JOBS IN SUSTAINABLE AQUACULTURE

AM03. PROMOTE SUSTAINABLE TOURISM AND RECREATION

AM04. IMPROVE WATER QUALITY AND CLEAN SEDIMENTS

AM05. DELIVER ROBUST PROTECTION OF MARINE BIODIVERSITY

AM06. ENHANCE RESILIENCE TO NATURAL HAZARDS AND FUTURE CLIMATE CHANGE

AM07. DEVELOP A CENTRALISED DATABASE AND KNOWLEDGE SHARING

AM08. ESTABLISH NEW GOVERNANCE AND FUNDING STRUCTURES

Protect and enhance natural capital

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Create and share knowledge

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Local and inclusive governance

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AM01. ACHIEVE SUSTAINABLE AND VIABLE WILD-CAPTURE FISHERIES

Objectives focus on

- Integration of fishery and environmental management
- Inclusion of local and anecdotal knowledge in decision making
- Supporting value-added benefits e.g. smokeries

• Fisheries Research & Management Plans

• Bristol Channel Herring Project

Benefits include

- Improved condition of key habitats will also protect biodiversity and increase carbon storage
- Partnership working and knowledge sharing between local stakeholders, regulators and scientists
- Ecosystem-based approach considers all industries and activities that impact fisheries
- Cultural heritage and livelihoods are celebrated and supported
- Additional research and evidence will inform better management of fisheries resources and their essential habitats

AM02. CREATE NEW JOBS IN SUSTAINABLE AQUACULTURE

- Recognises the potential for market diversification and job creation in a new sector
- Aims to take the opportunity to integrate sustainable practices from the outset

Benefits include

- New and existing businesses are supported which are models for sustainability and environmental consideration
- New sites are identified for seaweed culture which has commercial potential but also acts as a carbon store
- Locals and visitors to the area are encouraged to buy locally produced and sustainably sourced fish and aquaculture products
- Local economy is boosted and more resilient through diversification

AM03. PROMOTE SUSTAINABLE TOURISM AND RECREATION

- Tourism is key sector of North Devon economy
- Relies heavily on the natural environment and in some places pressures are at critical level
- Businesses see benefit of being greener in their approach as customers become more discerning
- Objectives focus on
 - Establishing codes of conduct for estuary users and recreational activities
 - Reducing disturbance for habitats and wildlife through voluntary agreements and eco-friendly alternatives
 - Accreditation schemes to promote awareness for businesses and consumers

Photo credit: North Devon AONB

AM04. IMPROVE WATER QUALITY AND CLEAN SEDIMENTS

- Aims to work alongside supportive farming policies and catchment management plan
- Acknowledges downstream impacts on marine environment from land practices
- Links with AM02 where there is potential for bioremediation from mussel sprat
- Supports local consortium in efforts to combat marine litter

Multiple benefits including

- Improved health and wellbeing for people
- Direct benefits for marine habitats and wildlife
- Enhanced fishery and shellfish productivity
- Systems approach to management of land, coast and sea
- Improved business, consumer and marine user awareness of marine pollution sources and impacts

AM05. DELIVER ROBUST PROTECTION OF MARINE BIODIVERSITY

High level aim to

- Protect the natural beauty and tranquillity of marine area for the local community and the economy
- Maintain healthy and functioning estuarine system to protect ecosystem services and allow full utilisation of natural capital
- To have the best managed MPAs in the UK
- Explicit recognition of the link between land, coast and sea in management decisions and impact assessment

- Objectives focus on
 - Incorporating principle of 'net gain' into MPA management
 - Co-management and local stewardship
 - Research and spatial monitoring
- Development of AM01-AM04 means that other plan objectives also support this aim

AM06. ENHANCE RESILIENCE TO NATURAL HAZARDS AND FUTURE CLIMATE CHANGE

- Focuses on enhancement and protection of natural capital such as saltmarsh to increase resilience
- Links with AM02 to increase 'blue' carbon in Taw-Torridge estuary
- Recognises potential for renewable energy projects in the area (and need to establish criteria for local buy-in)
- Development of AM01-AM04 means that other plan objectives also support this aim

AM07. DEVELOP A CENTRALISED DATABASE AND KNOWLEDGE SHARING

Key function of the Biosphere Reserve is to research, monitor and disseminate learning from our approaches to sustainable development (BR Strategy 2014-2024)

- Objectives focus on
 - Voluntary agreements with fishermen to supply spatial-data on catch and effort
 - Implement codes of conduct and regular monitoring surveys
 - Citizen science programmes and data collation
 - Research agenda for key knowledge gaps

Geodatabase and GeoNode

- Baseline of marine information for managers of the North Devon Biosphere Reserve
- Indication of what data are currently lacking and need further research
- Decision support tool for future management of marine areas

AM08. ESTABLISH NEW GOVERNANCE AND FUNDING STRUCTURES

- Objectives focus on
 - Strengthening communication and coordination between local stakeholders and regulatory agencies
 - Appointment of Estuary Officer and Marine Coordinator roles to support delivery, monitoring and review of marine management objectives
 - Formalising the role of the North Devon Biosphere Marine Working Group and sub-groups
 - Establishment of local delivery body for ‘blue’ natural capital trust

The Marine Pioneer demonstrated that excellent partnership working between different agencies was possible, both across sectors and from a local to national level

Ensuring this collaborative approach continues will be a key legacy beyond the end of the Marine Pioneer timeline

What makes good governance?

4 principles

- **Leadership, direction, and accountability**
- **Localisation** (the principle of subsidiarity)
- **Adaptive management**
- **Information flow and transparency**

Governance structures

National and International

Regional

Area based partnerships

Local site/theme specific groups

Governance of the plan

Governance of the plan

Sustainable finance and investment

Sustainable finance models

- Blue Impact fund (WWF/Environmental Finance)
- Local Natural Capital Trust (Biosphere Foundation)

Investment opportunities

- Enhanced fisheries management
- Improving water quality
- Reducing impact on wildlife
- Enhancing carbon storage and natural flood management

Monitoring and evaluation

- Reviewed every five years to provide feedback for decision-makers
- Development of Natural Capital Asset and Risk Register identified indicators for each objective
- Indicators added to the GeoNode (where data available) to spatially monitor and review progress
- Proposed governance structure will allow for adaptive management outside of these timescales

What have we learned so far?

- It's difficult to do for Marine – NC objectives work over different spatial scales than management and governance scales
- It's a good opportunity to look at governance under a NC lens and bring different people together to have the discussion - businesses, tourism and recreation, maritime industry, fisheries, conservation, regulation.
- Our plan became a Natural Capital Plan *plus* – not all of the goals defined at a local level were a good fit with the NCA. People place value on things that are not considered by a natural capital approach alone.
- The plan as it stands will not deliver *significant* NC improvements in the short term but it sets the road map - building social capital (groups, relationships, networking) and human capital (skills and knowledge) in the short term to deliver long term benefits to nature and us.
- To deliver some of the benefits to nature and drive innovation, there needs to be policy changes at a national level and a willingness to do something a bit different - test things in a place, before they become policy.
- That we will learn more when we deliver it.

Thank you

Any questions?

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Photo: 361 Aerial Media